

Transformative Pathways and Challenges in Fisheries Governance: The case of the Octopus Fishery in the Yucatán Peninsula, Mexico

Katina Roumbedakis¹, Silvia Salas², Cristina Pita^{1,3}, Graham J. Pierce¹

¹Instituto de Investigaciones Mariñas, (IIM-CSIC), Vigo, Spain

²Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados, Unidad Mérida, Mérida, Yucatán, México

³CESAM - Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies, Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Abstract: Small-scale fisheries (SSF) are vital for food security, livelihoods, community wellbeing and the cultural identity of coastal communities, especially in developing countries. However, the sustainability of SSF is increasingly threatened by ecological, socio-economic, and governance challenges. Additionally, the inherent diversity, complexity, and ever-changing dynamics of the fishing communities play a central role in shaping the structure and long-term viability of fisheries supply chains. In this line, there is no 'one-size-fits-all' ruling for SSF effective management. Using as a case study the octopus' fishery of the Yucatán Peninsula, Mexico, this study aims to understand and analyse the governance transformations associated with the octopus fishery. This fishery is characterized by its dynamic and seasonal nature, generating around 35,000 jobs in the region. Nonetheless, this fishery faces several stressors including climate change, illegal fishing, overexploitation, and shifting market demands. Hence the Mexican octopus fisheries governance is undergoing continuous transformations. Despite current and past efforts to implement effective management strategies, governance in this fishery remains fragmented and top-down, with limited stakeholder engagement in the decision-making processes. Allied to this, poor surveillance and lack of effective compliance mechanisms threaten the sustainability and equitable management of SSF for octopus. Understanding the evolution and transformation of governance in SSF is crucial for recognizing how policies and management systems adapt to changing conditions. We will discuss the main governance challenges and future opportunities.

Keywords: small-scale fisheries, ocean governance, challenges, opportunities, sustainability

